

Please answer the following questions (in order) and fill the required information in the table given.

1. What kind of workplace is easy/comfortable for you to work in?

- **Please list five things** that you think are important.
- Please be specific in your answer, using sentences instead of words.

2. To what extent have these five things been fulfilled?

- How many points (**out of 100**) would you give to **each of the five items**?

3. How would you rank the five items in order of importance?

- **Please state the percentage of each item so that the total of the five items adds up to 100%.**

	1. What kind of workplace is easy/comfortable for you to work in?	2. To what extent have these five things been fulfilled? (out of 100)	3. How would you rank the five items in order of importance? (the total of the five items adds up to 100%)
1		points	+ %
2		points	+ %
3		points	+ %
4		points	+ %
5		points	+ %
			Total <u>100 %</u>